

**SYNTHESIS OF 2': 4'-DIHYDROXY-5'-BROMOCHALKONE DERIVATIVES.
EFFECT OF BROMINE ATOM AND A FREE HYDROXY GROUP IN
THE PHENYL RING ON THE FORMATION OF FLAVONOLS**

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2': 4'-Dihydroxy-5'-bromoalkones have been synthesised by condensing 2,4-dihydroxy-5-bromoacetophenone with aromatic aldehydes in presence of 40% NaOH and have been converted into their respective flavonols.

Substituted acetophenones have been condensed with aldehydes to obtain the corresponding chalcones (Göschka and Tambor, *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 3503; Shinoda *et al.*, *J. Pharm. Soc., Japan*, 1929, 49, 123; Saiyad *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1737). Resacetophenone condenses rather with difficulty with the aldehydes like benzaldehyde, anisaldehyde, etc. Monomethyl ether of resacetophenone and its monobromo derivatives afford chalcones and flavonols easily (Marathey and Athavale, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 654). So it will be of interest to ascertain whether monobromo-resacetophenone condenses with aldehydes like benzaldehyde, anisaldehyde, nitrobenzaldehyde, and piperonal. Bromination of the resacetophenone in acetic acid medium yielded a product which was found identical with 2: 4-dihydroxy-5-bromoacetophenone (Delhiwala and Shah, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1941, 13A, 352). The condensation of the ketone with different aldehydes shows that the presence of the bromine atom in the nucleus together with two hydroxy groups facilitates the formation of chalcone; but its presence hinders to some extent the formation of flavonol.

EXPERIMENTAL

2: 4-Dihydroxy-5-bromoacetophenone.—To a solution of resacetophenone (0.7 g.) in 60% acetic acid (5 c.c.) was added a 25% solution of bromine (3.2 c.c.) in acetic acid. The solution became hot (exothermic reaction) and yellowish white crystals began to appear on scratching the sides of the beaker. The crude product after filtration at the pump was crystallised from glacial acetic acid as white crystals (0.5 g.), m.p. 164°. (Found: Br, 34.0. Calc. Br, 34.6%). It dissolves in NaOH solution and develops a deep brown coloration with ethanolic ferric chloride. It is soluble in common organic solvents but is insoluble in water (*cf.* resacetophenone).

The condensation of ketone with (i) benzaldehyde, (ii) *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde, (iii) anisaldehyde, and (iv) piperonal was carried out in the following manner :

To a solution of the ketone (0.5 g.) in ethanol (10 c.c.) was added the aldehyde (1 c.c. or 1 g.). To the homogeneous solution 40% NaOH solution (2 c.c.) was added and the mixture was left for about 36 hours. The solution was acidified, treated with NaHCO₃ solution to remove the acid formed in the side reaction, and the crude mass was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in each case. The yield, m.p., and the m.p. of the acetal derivatives are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I
Chalkone.

Aldehyde.	Yield.	M.P.	M.P. of acetal derivative.	% Bromine.	
				Found.	Calc.
Benzaldehyde	0.32 g.	162°	..	24.6	25.0
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	0.30	213°	235	21.3	21.9
Anisaldehyde	0.35	173	166°	22.5	22.9
Piperonal	0.37	280	130°	21.5	22.0

It is interesting to note that the ketone also condenses smoothly with the aromatic aldehyde (excluding hydroxyaldehydes) by the sodium peroxide method (Marathey, *J. Univ. Poona*, 1956, 8, 76). This method has the advantage over the other methods in having the time required reduced from 36 hours to 30 minutes and the yield to the same extent.

The above chalkones were condensed into their respective flavonols by the sodium peroxide method (Marathey, *loc. cit.*). The m.p.s. of the flavonols are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Flavonol.	M.P.
7-Hydroxy-6-bromo-	168°
7-Hydroxy-6-bromo-3'-nitro-	240°
7-Hydroxy-6-bromo-4'-methoxy-	235°
7-Hydroxy-6-bromo-3':4'-dioxymethylene-	240°